

Survey on the Evaluation of the RDMTraining4NFDI Hybrid Training Event for Research Data Management

Introduction

The RDMTraining4NFDI Hybrid Training Event on Research Data Management (RDM)¹ was designed for both beginners and experienced professionals in RDM who provide, or plan to provide generic and/or discipline-specific training.

Organized by RDMTraining4NFDI and enriched with insights from experienced external trainers, the program offered a dynamic mix of learning formats (on-site, online, self-learning path and asynchronous homework). Where possible, parallel sessions were tailored to different experience levels. Participants had the flexibility to register for one, several, or all event formats, depending on their interests and availability.

The goals of this training event were to:

- Deliver practical, focused RDM guidance within a condensed time frame.
- Strengthen participants' training skills (including didactics) and data management expertise.
- Foster the exchange of best practices within the RDM community.
- Experiment with and evaluate diverse training formats.²

Data for the evaluation of the modules within the Hybrid Event was collected through surveys. The goal of the survey was to gather anonymous feedback from participants on satisfaction, practical application, and content.

The survey responses were only used for internal analysis and service development. Processing was based on the participant's consent (Art. 6(1)(a) GDPR). The survey was conducted using 2ask³. The data was stored securely and analyzed only by the RDMTraining4NFDI team.

Participants have the opportunity to withdraw the consent or request deletion of their data at any time by contacting rdmtraining4nfdi-orga@lists.nfdi.de.

¹ Vandendorpe, J., Wohltmann, M., & Müller, R., 2025

² Müller, R. *et al.*, 2024

³ provided by orbiz Software GmbH, Robert-Gerwig-Str. 4, 78467 Konstanz. The collected data was handled in accordance with GDPR and was not transferred outside Germany. 2ask used cookies to ensure website functionality and a user-friendly design. For more information, please refer to [2ask's Privacy Policy](#). Please note that this link leads to the provider's website, which may use Google Analytics.

By completing the survey, the participants confirmed that they had read, understood and accepted this privacy notice.

How to Read the Surveys

In total, five surveys were conducted to evaluate:

- The on-site training module (Survey Module)
- The self-learning module (Survey on Self-Learning Modules)
- The interactive workshop on Python (Survey on Python): Pre, Post- and second Post-Survey

This document compiles the original questions from each survey, organised by survey.

Survey Module

This survey took place two days after the on-site training module (Strategic Data Stewardship & Change Management) and directly after each of the online modules (Foundations of RDM for beginners, Practical Data Protection in Research, Python for beginners, Git for beginners, Git for advanced, Introduction to Galaxy, Didactics & Motivation). In total, the on-site and online workshop ran from 28th of October 2025 until 20th of November 2025.

Q1 Which module would you like to evaluate? If you participated in more than one module, please use one survey for each. (Mandatory, Single Option)

- *Strategic Data Stewardship & Change Management (28 + 29 Oct 2025)*⁴
- *Foundations of RDM for beginners (4 Nov 2025)*⁵
- *Practical Data Protection in Research (6 Nov 2025)*⁶
- *Python for beginners (11 Nov 2025)*⁷
- *Git for beginners (13 Nov 2025)*⁸
- *Git for advanced (13 Nov 2025)*⁹
- *Introduction to Galaxy (18 Nov 2025)*¹⁰
- *Didactics & Motivation (20 Nov 2025)*¹¹

Q2 From my perspective, ... (Optional, Single Option for each scale, Likert Scale [too low, somewhat too low, suitable, somewhat too high, too high])

⁴ Manske, A., & Zänkert, S., 2024

⁵ Vandendorpe, J., & Boße, S., 2025

⁶ Vishen, N., 2025

⁷ Förstner, K. *et al.* 2025a and 2025b

⁸ McAulay, E. *et al.* 2023

⁹ Schlauch, T. *et al.* 2023

¹⁰ Fouilloux, A. *et al.* n.d. and Kamieniecka, K. *et al.* n.d.

¹¹ Müller, R., & Wohltmann, M., 2025

- the amount of content of the module was
- the amount of new information was
- the exercises' level of difficulty was
- the number of exercises was
- the content encouraged my level of participation

Q3 Would you like to share any comments (e.g., topics you think should be covered in the workshop or further suggestions for improvements)? *(Optional, free text)*

Q4 Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements: *(Optional, Single Option for each scale, Likert Scale [Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, Strongly Agree])*

- The workshop is designed to meet the needs / expectations and answer the questions of the target group.
- The workshop is suitable for the provided format (e.g. online, in-person, self-learning).
- The workshop effectively complements my daily working matters.
- The workshop highly raised my interest in the topic.
- The trainer of the workshop appeared knowledgeable.

Q5 How helpful was the workshop for your work as an RDM multiplier? *(Optional, Single Option, Likert Scale [Not helpful, Somewhat helpful, Neutral, Helpful, Very Helpful])*

Q6 How confident are you in applying this knowledge to your daily work? *(Optional, Single Option, Likert Scale [Not confident at all, Slightly confident, Neutral, Confident, Very Confident])*

Q7 How satisfied are you overall with the workshop?*(Optional, Single Option, Likert Scale [Very dissatisfied, Dissatisfied, Neutral, Satisfied, Very satisfied])*

Q8 Would you like to share any comments (e.g., suggestions for the format that might work best for the topic or ideas for improvement)? *(Optional, free text)*

Survey Self-Learning Module

Participants were asked to explore the self-learning modules¹² from 3rd November 2025 until 11th December 2025, the official closing date of the Hybrid Event. The survey link was included at the end of the self-learning module in LIA Script¹³.

¹²

https://liascript.github.io/course/?https://raw.githubusercontent.com/MUebachs/RDMTraining4NFDI_Hybrid-Event-Research_Data_Management_for-NFDI_Consortia/refs/heads/main/README.md#1

¹³https://www.google.com/url?q=https://liascript.github.io/course/?https://raw.githubusercontent.com/MUebachs/RDMTraining4NFDI_Hybrid-Event-Research_Data_Management_for-NFDI_Consortia/refs/h

Q1 Which of the following modules did you complete? (Select all that apply)
(Mandatory, Multiple Options)

- *Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management*
- *Open Research*
- *Intermediate Research Software Development (Python)*
- *Version Control*
- *DMP4NFDI Train-the-Trainer Concept on Data Management Plans and RDMO*
- *Data Sharing and Publishing*

Q2 Which of the following modules did you start but not complete? (Select all that apply) (Mandatory, MultipleOptions)

- *Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management*
- *Open Research*
- *Intermediate Research Software Development (Python)*
- *Version Control*
- *DMP4NFDI Train-the-Trainer Concept on Data Management Plans and RDMO*
- *Data Sharing and Publishing*
- *None*

Q3 What were the reasons you did not complete these modules? (Question was skipped, if Q2 none; free text)

Q4 Did you attempt the exercises in the completed module(s)? (Optional, Single Option for each scale, Scale [Not at all, Some of them, All of them, N.A.]

- *Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management*
- *Open Research*
- *Intermediate Research Software Development (Python)*
- *Version Control*
- *DMP4NFDI Train-the-Trainer Concept on Data Management Plans and RDMO*
- *Data Sharing and Publishing*

Q5 Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statement: The instructions for the exercises of the module were clear. (Optional, Single Option for each scale, Likert Scale [Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, Strongly Agree, N.A.]

- *Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management*
- *Open Research*
- *Intermediate Research Software Development (Python)*

eprints.ox.ac.uk/main/README.md%231&sa=D&source=docs&ust=1767871224457947&usg=AOvVaw337QGJraLtGVJ5cD2oUmJf

- *Version Control*
- *DMP4NFDI Train-the-Trainer Concept on Data Management Plans and RDMO*
- *Data Sharing and Publishing*

Q6 Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statement: The exercises' level of difficulty was suitable. *(Optional, Single Option for each scale, Likert Scale [Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, Strongly Agree, N.A.]*)

- *Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management*
- *Open Research*
- *Intermediate Research Software Development (Python)*
- *Version Control*
- *DMP4NFDI Train-the-Trainer Concept on Data Management Plans and RDMO*
- *Data Sharing and Publishing*

Q7 Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statement: The exercises encouraged my participation. *(Optional, Single Option for each scale, Likert Scale [Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, Strongly Agree, N.A.]*)

- *Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management*
- *Open Research*
- *Intermediate Research Software Development (Python)*
- *Version Control*
- *DMP4NFDI Train-the-Trainer Concept on Data Management Plans and RDMO*
- *Data Sharing and Publishing*

Q8 Which exercise was your favorite and why? *(Optional, free text)*

Q9 Which exercises did not work well and why? *(Optional, free text)*

Q10 Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statement: A Self-Learning Training is suitable for the module. *(Optional, Single Option for each scale, Likert Scale [Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, Strongly Agree, N.A.]*)

- *Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management*
- *Open Research*
- *Intermediate Research Software Development (Python)*
- *Version Control*
- *DMP4NFDI Train-the-Trainer Concept on Data Management Plans and RDMO*
- *Data Sharing and Publishing*

Q11 Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statement: The length of the module was appropriate to achieve the learning goals. *(Optional, Single*

Option for each scale, Likert Scale [Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, Strongly Agree, N.A.]

- *Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management*
- *Open Research*
- *Intermediate Research Software Development (Python)*
- *Version Control*
- *DMP4NFDI Train-the-Trainer Concept on Data Management Plans and RDMO*
- *Data Sharing and Publishing*

Q12 Which format did you prefer for the learning materials? (Select all that apply)

(Optional, Multiple Options)

- *Book (e.g. Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management)*
- *Handbook (e.g. The Turing Way)*
- *Lesson (e.g. The Carpentries)*
- *Project Deliverables (e.g. DMP4NFDI Train-the-Trainer Concept in Data Management Plans and RDMO)*
- *Slides (e.g. Data Sharing and Publishing)*

Q13 How helpful was the content of the module(s) for your daily work as a RDM multiplier? (Optional, Single Option for each scale, Likert Scale [Not helpful, Somewhat helpful, Neutral, Helpful, Very Helpful, N.A.]

- *Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management*
- *Open Research*
- *Intermediate Research Software Development (Python)*
- *Version Control*
- *DMP4NFDI Train-the-Trainer Concept on Data Management Plans and RDMO*
- *Data Sharing and Publishing*

Q14 How confident are you in applying this knowledge to your daily work?

(Optional, Single Option for each scale, Likert Scale [Not confident at all, Slightly confident, Neutral, Confident, Very Confident, N.A.]

- *Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management*
- *Open Research*
- *Intermediate Research Software Development (Python)*
- *Version Control*
- *DMP4NFDI Train-the-Trainer Concept on Data Management Plans and RDMO*
- *Data Sharing and Publishing*

Q15 How satisfied are you with: (Optional, Single Option for each scale, Likert Scale [Very dissatisfied, Dissatisfied, Neutral, Satisfied, Very satisfied; N.A.]

- *the Self-Learning in total*
- *Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management*
- *Open Research*
- *Intermediate Research Software Development (Python)*
- *Version Control*
- *DMP4NFDI Train-the-Trainer Concept on Data Management Plans and RDMO*
- *Data Sharing and Publishing*

Q8 Are there any other comments or suggestions for improvement? (*Optional, free text*)

Survey on Python

The Python survey took place immediately before the workshop¹⁴ (Pre-Survey), immediately after the workshop (Post-Survey), and one and a half weeks after the workshop (Post-Survey Part Two). The survey was adapted from those created by The Carpentries.¹⁵ In both Post-Surveys only Q1 + Q4 were asked.

Q1 Please enter a unique identifier as follows: Number of siblings (as numeric) + first two letters of the city you were born in (lower case) + first three letters of your current street (lower case).

Example: If I have 0 siblings, was born in Arlington, and live on Creekwater Street, my unique identifier would be 0arcre. (*Mandatory, Free text*)

Q2 How often do you currently use a programming language (R, Python, etc.)? (*Only asked in the Pre-Survey, Optional, Single Option, Likert Scale (never, less than once per year, several times per year, monthly, weekly, daily)*)

Q3 Please rate your level of satisfaction with your current data management and analysis workflow (i.e. how you collect, organize, store and analyze your data). (*Only asked in the Pre-Survey, Optional, Single Option, Likert Scale (Strongly dissatisfied, Dissatisfied, Somewhat dissatisfied, Neutral, Somewhat satisfied, Satisfied, Strongly Satisfied)*)

Q4 Please rate your level of agreement with the following statements: (*Optional, Single Option for each scale, Likert Scale [Strongly dissatisfied, Dissatisfied, Somewhat dissatisfied, Neutral, Somewhat satisfied, Satisfied, Strongly Satisfied]*)

- *Having access to the original, raw data is important to be able to repeat an analysis.*
- *I can write a small program, script, or macro to address a problem in my own work.*

¹⁴ Förstner, K. U., et al., 2025

¹⁵ <https://carpentries.org/>

- *I know how to search for answers to my technical questions online.*
- *If I got stuck while working on a programming project, I can find ways of overcoming the problem.*
- *I am confident in my ability to make use of programming software to work with data.*
- *Using a programming language (like R or Python) can make my analyses easier to reproduce.*
- *Using a programming language (like R or Python) can make me more efficient at working with data.*

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